

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF SHORTENED WORDS AND ABBREVIATIONS IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

Linguistics is an independent science that studies the language of mankind, studies the emergence and development of language, language and thought, the relationship between language and society, the role of language in society, its internal structure - the classification of language, the methods of its analysis and the like. In this article, the abbreviations that are considered to be the part of linguistics, the concepts of abbreviation, the rules of their legalization, as well as the aspects of difference and similarity, are discussed.

As we know, linguistics is an independent science that studies the language of mankind, along with this term, the term linguistics is widely used in scientific sources. Linguistics is a science that studies the emergence and development of language, language and thought, the relationship between language and society, the role of language in society, its internal structure - the classification of language, the methods of its analysis and the like. Language is a system of phonetic, lexical and grammatical means that serve in the expression of thoughts, feelings, desires, etc.; it is a social phenomenon that serves as the main and most important means of communication, thinking among people. Shortened words, abbreviation which are considered to be the part of linguistics, have been studied by a number of scientists over the years and are studied in many scientific sources. In the study of these concepts scientists such as, O.

Jespersion, G. Cannon, L. Blumfield, N.N.Alekseyeva, V.P.Korovushkin, L.B.Tkacheva, V.V.Borisov, I.V. Arnold, M.T.Iriskulov, A. Khodjiev made their great contributions. In linguistics, the concepts of shortened words and abbreviations are used widely. Although there is almost no significant difference between these terms, each of them has been studied as a separate term.

If we consider these terms as a separate concept, then each of them is described as follows in the sources on linguistics:

Words obtained as a result of a reduction are called shortened words or complex words. Shortened words are words that are formed by the addition of capital letters or a certain part of these independent word combinations. We can see the shortened words in the examples below:

LC-Land Cadastre

UN - United Nations

DIB-Department of Internal Affairs

Shortened words appeared firstly in written speech due to the need to achieve compactness in the process of speech, and then began to be used even in oral speech. Shortened words, mainly belonging to the category of nouns, are formed through the following methods:

- 1) by adding the first letters of the word combination components. For example, SSE is the State Standard of Education, NTRC is the National television-radio company; this type of shortening is also called abbreviation in scientific literature;
- 2) the word combination is formed by taking 1st syllable of the word 1 in the composition, and adding 1st letters of the remaining words .For example, UzNU-Uzbekistan National University, UzLA-Uzbek literature and art;
- 3) by taking out the main parts of the words in the composition of the word combination - Biofac-Faculty of biology, Philfac-Faculty of Philology;
- 4) by adding 1st syllable of the word in the composition of the word combination, and without reducing the remaining words-UzGasOil;
- 5) through a mixed way-Uzbektelecom, Uzteleradiocompany and others, we can illustrate these as an example.

The shortened words denote the names of international organizations (UN, UNESCO), countries and states (UAE, RF, USA), Political Parties, military associations (UzLiDP, NATO), scientific and educational institutions (UzASc, UzWLSU, BSU), ministries, offices, institutions, organizations, enterprises (MHE, STC, Uzmashkholding , UzGasOil), machinery, equipment and structures (ECM, HES) and others. Abbreviated words can either be

borrowed from other languages (UNESCO, FIFA, FIDE, NATO) or they can be formed on the basis of lexical units of a particular language, for example, Uzbek. Most of the Uzbek abbreviations, belonging to the next type ,are Russian word combinations and excerpts from the abbreviations based on them, for example, such as BMT-OOH, DAN-ГАИ, OAV - СММ [5].

In contrast to shortened words, abbreviation is derived from Italian word "abbreviature" and Latin word "abbreviation", means abbreviation, abbreviated. In linguistics, the abbreviation is considered to be the words formed by shortening the word combinations . The abbreviation is divided into the following types: a) the words in the word combination are spelled in alphabetical order of the first letters, or simple words – letters are pronounced as sounds mean. For example, Uzbek OTM (o-te-em) is Higher educational institution, Uzbek MDH (em-de-he) is the Commonwealth of independent states; b) complex abbreviated words: in addition to the first letters of the word combinations, certain parts of them (morphemes) are added. For Example, Uzbek O'zRes.- The Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbek Filfak (Faculty of philology) [6];

In conclusion, based on the foregoing ,shortened words in linguistics possess a broad semantic concept, are formed according to several types of rules. For example, the Uzbek MDH, O'z.Res, Filfak and others. And the abbreviation is type of the shortened words, which are formed by adding the first letters of the word combination components. We can say as an example Uzbek OTM, BMT, EHM , etc.

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